

EVSE Metrological Verification through IEC 61851 Protocol Hacking

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Abstract—As EU countries approved the phaseout of CO₂-emitting cars by 2035, electric vehicle technology is set to become predominant in the passenger car market. As a result, an increasing number of Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE) installations will be deployed across countries. Since these installations are measurement instruments, they will require periodic metrological verification. This paper focuses on the development and testing of field equipment for the metrological verification of the EVSE metering subsystem. A Man In the Middle (MIM) approach has been used to hack the communication line between the EVSE and the Electric Vehicle (EV), in order to force the EV to draw different current levels and to test the EVSE under several operating conditions. The test equipment was developed and tested at the University of Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli" in Aversa, Italy.

Keywords— *Battery Electric Vehicle, e-Mobility, Power Measurement, Energy Measurement, Metrological Verification, Protocol Hacking.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The European Union (EU) has identified Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) vehicles as one of the main sources of environmental pollution due to emissions from exhaust gases (not only CO₂). Currently, almost 300 million cars are in circulation in Europe, with an average age of about 12 years. Despite a significant increase in sales in recent years, alternative fuel vehicles represent only 5.3% of the total number of cars in the EU. Battery Electric Vehicles (EVs) and Plug-in Hybrid EVs account for only 0.5% and 0.6% of the car fleet, respectively, while 1.2% of all cars on EU roads are hybrid EVs. This scenario has recently led EU countries to introduce a ban on internal combustion engine cars in order to accelerate the transition to more sustainable transportation solutions.

Recently, EU countries have approved a historic law that will end the sale of new vehicles with CO₂ emissions by 2035. Approval by the energy ministers of EU countries means that the main European climate policy for cars can now be implemented. The EU law will require all new cars sold to have zero CO₂ emissions from 2035 onwards and to reduce CO₂ emissions by 55% from 2030, compared to 2021 levels. The objectives are designed to promote rapid decarbonization of the new car fleet in Europe.

Fully electric vehicles operate exclusively on electric power. They are powered by one or more electric motors powered by rechargeable batteries. EVs have several benefits over conventional vehicles. First, they are environmentally friendly as they do not emit pollutants from the exhaust; pollutants can generally be produced by power plants generating the energy, but electric energy produced from nuclear, hydro, solar, or wind power does not emit atmospheric pollutants. Additionally, EVs are more energy-efficient, converting over 77% of electric energy from the grid into energy at the wheels [1], [2], while traditional gasoline vehicles convert only about 12-30% of the energy stored in gasoline into energy at the wheels [3]. Obviously, there are other performance advantages as well. Electric motors offer quiet, smooth operation, stronger acceleration, and require less maintenance than internal combustion engines (ICEs). Not least, the EU's energy dependence, especially on fossil fuels, can be significantly reduced through electrification. This, coupled with increased adoption of renewable energy sources, can lead to a more sustainable future. EU policymakers are making significant efforts in this direction [4].

Of course, EVs have some disadvantages compared to gasoline cars. They have a limited driving range compared to internal combustion engine vehicles, and fully charging the battery pack can take a long time. Even fast charging to 80% capacity can take over 30 minutes. Improving driving range and reducing charging time are crucial goals to promote the adoption of this new technology. The best way to achieve this goal is to improve efficiency, as this not only improves range and reduces charging time but also lowers overall consumption.

A significant portion of energy is lost in transmission from the grid to the battery. Specifically, during battery charging, energy is lost in converting alternating current (AC) from the grid to direct current (DC) for use in the battery, as well as overcoming battery resistance during charging, which increases as the battery approaches its maximum capacity. Charging losses can vary depending on the specific vehicle, type of charging system used, battery state, and environmental conditions (weather).

In a context of increasing adoption of electric mobility, accurate measurement of energy flows between charging station and vehicle plays a crucial role. Such measurement of energy transferred from the charging station to the car is not only the basis for energy payment but is necessary to assess the performance of Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) and Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE), improving the efficiency of the charging process, thereby contributing to overall performance improvements.

Field measurements can be a valuable tool for customers in choosing a BEV and EVSE, as well as for designers to properly assess efficiency to design higher performance systems and further reduce the environmental impact of these new technologies. Moreover, given the potential for BEVs to feed energy back into the grid when needed, utilizing emerging Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technologies, EVs must be considered integrated into the power grid, acting as distributed energy resources. Consequently, precise energy measurement is essential for optimizing the efficiency of the entire electricity network.

It is important to note that, similarly to regular checks at traditional gasoline pumps, EVSE should also be calibrated and undergo periodic metrological checks, especially in the presence of Power Quality (PQ) disturbances [5]. The measurement part of EVSE can be classified as MI-003 (active electrical energy meters) in accordance with European Directive MID 2014/32/EU [6], at least in countries where the directive has been transposed. This approach helps ensure measurement accuracy and, consequently, the correctness of energy payment, promoting efficient and transparent management of electric charging stations.

A calibration setup for on-field metrological verification of EVSE has been already presented in [7], the work aims to insert a measurement system between the EVSE and the BEV, in order to test the EVSE metering subsystem adopting the BEV as load. In addition, the present work proposes an innovative solution that enables testing the EVSE under various operating conditions, providing the ability to adjust the current absorbed by the BEV. Preliminary results from the field characterization of an AC charging station using the designed instrumentation will be presented.

II. CHARGING MODE, CONNECTIONS AND SIGNALING

The BEV charging reference standard is IEC 61851-1 [8], while IEC 62196 defines plugs, socket outlets, vehicle connectors, and vehicle inlets [9].

There are four charging modes. The first two, Mode 1 and Mode 2, are only allowed for private charging and prohibited in public areas. Mode 1 consists directly connecting the EV to standard current sockets without special safety systems, and is typically used for charging e-bikes or scooters. The rated current and voltage values should not exceed 16 A and 250 V in single-phase or 16 A and 480 V in three-phase. Mode 2 requires a specific safety system between the connection point and the vehicle. It can be used with both domestic and industrial sockets, with rated current and voltage values not exceeding 32 A and 250 V in single-phase or 32 A and 480 V in three-phase.

Mode 3 involves charging the vehicle through a power supply system permanently connected to the electrical network. This is the mode of most of existing EVSE in Italy, all automatic AC charging systems. It is the only mode

allowed for public AC charging, typically supporting up to 32 A and 250 V in single-phase or up to 32 A and 480 V in three-phase, although legislation may not set limits.

Mode 4 is the only mode providing Direct Current (DC). The energy is sent directly to the battery bypassing the onboard charger. It provides a maximum voltage of 600 V DC and current values up to 400 A, requiring advanced communication and security features due to high-power levels. For Mode 4, an AC/DC power converter integrated into the EVSE is necessary, resulting in a larger charging station due to the converter transforming AC current into DC before reaching the electric car via the charging cable.

This paper focuses on testing Mode 3 AC EVSE, as it is currently the most widely adopted solution in the EU. In the EU, AC three-phase voltage has been harmonized to 400 V RMS, with EVSE typically operating at 400 V phase-to-phase voltage and a maximum current of 32 A, resulting in a maximum available charging power of 22 kW.

Mode 3 and Mode 4 connectors have a pin named Control Pilot (CP), dedicated to the communications used to negotiate charging between EV and EVSE [9]. CP signals are used in EV technology to communicate information between power sources, substations, and EV, it allows to control the charge process or the vehicle to grid (V2G).

The reference standard [8] provides the following electrical diagram for the communication between EVSE and EV (see Fig. 1). Inside EVSE, there is an oscillator which generates a PWM signal ($\pm 12V$, 1 kHz). On the EV side, there are two resistors whose parallel value is regulated by a switch.

The CP line is a standard feature across all types of vehicle connectors used for electric vehicles (EVs), regardless of the specific connector type. The CP line is essential for facilitating communication between the vehicle's On-Board Charger (OBC) and the EVSE, ensuring safe and efficient charging operations. It conveys important information such as the charging system state, maximum charging current, and any error messages between the vehicle and the charging infrastructure. Therefore, whether it's a Type 1 (SAE J1772), Type 2 (IEC 62196), CHAdeMO (CHARge de MOve), CCS (Combined Charging System), or any other connector type, the presence of the CP line is fundamental for proper charging functionality.

When the vehicle and EVSE are disconnected, the CP line on the vehicle side, between the OBC and the charging port, maintains a 0 V potential (due to R_2 presence on the EV side), while the EVSE side holds a 12 V potential (the EVSE side square wave oscillator is initially turned off.).

Upon initial connection, the CP line acts as a potential divider circuit, created between the 12 V source (in the EVSE) and a ground (in the OBC), utilizing two resistors (one in the EVSE and the other in the OBC). Consequently, the CP line voltage drops to 9 V. This change in CP line voltage signals to the EVSE the establishment of a solid connection with the vehicle's OBC. Once confirmed, the EVSE switches the CP line circuit source from a constant 12 V supply to a PWM generating source, producing a square wave switching at 1,000 kHz (1,000 cycles per second), ranging between -12 V and 12 V.

Fig. 1. CP electrical diagram

During the switching cycle, when the source voltage is positive (+12 V), the diode closes the connection between CP and the resistors in the OBC, resulting in a voltage drop across the resistor R1 (in the EVSE), thereby generating a 9 V potential on the CP line. Conversely, when the source voltage is at -12 V, the diode in the OBC effectively interrupts the circuit, causing no potential difference across R1 and presenting the full -12 V potential on the CP line. The OBC can close the S2 switch to increase the voltage drop, signalling the need for ventilation (in which case the EVSE supplies charging power only if the area is ventilated). The peak CP line voltage (as measured on EV side) indicates the actual charging state (see Table 1).

TABLE I. PEAK CP VOLTAGE MEANING

Peak Voltage	State	Description
+12 V	State A	No EV connected to the EVSE
+9 V	State B	EV connected to the EVSE, but not ready for charging
+6 V	State C	Connected and ready for charging, ventilation is not required
+3 V	State D	Connected, ready for charging and ventilation is required
+0 V	State E	Electrical short to earth on the controller of the EVSE, no power supply
-12 V	State F	EVSE is unavailable

The EVSE adapts the PWM duty cycle based on the available maximum charging current. The table 2 outlines the approximate relationship between the two. The amount of current available depends not only on the specifications of the EVSE itself and the electrical wiring and infrastructure that support it but also on the power availability at the moment of charging, which can vary with grid demand.

III. EVSE CALIBRATION

There are several types of charging systems available for electric vehicles. When considering public charging stations, which are typically situated in publicly accessible areas such as parking lots, it's crucial for these installations to accurately measure the energy dispensed to facilitate commercial transactions. From a technical point of view, the calibration of these meters is similar to that of a wattmeter or energy meter (apart from the connection already resolved in [7]). Thus, calibrating an EVSE requires introducing a reference wattmeter. This wattmeter will be inserted, as usual, between the power source and the load. Depending on the specific type of charging station, it needs a single-phase AC, three-phase AC, or DC wattmeter. In any scenario, it's essential to measure voltages and currents using an external reference instrument for error estimation.

TABLE II. PWM DUTY CYCLE MEANING

Duty cycle	Maximum current to be drawn by EV
Duty cycle < 3%	Charging not allowed
$3\% \leq \text{Duty cycle} \leq 7\%$	Indicates that digital communication will be used to control an off-board DC charger or communicate available line current for an on-board charger. Digital communication may also be used with other duty cycles. Charging is not allowed without digital communication.
$7\% < \text{Duty cycle} < 8\%$	Charging not allowed
$8\% \leq \text{Duty cycle} < 10\%$	6 A
$10\% \leq \text{Duty cycle} \leq 85\%$	Available current = (%duty cycle) \times 0.6 A
$85\% < \text{Duty cycle} \leq 96\%$	Available current = (%duty cycle - 64) \times 2.5 A
$96\% < \text{Duty cycle} \leq 97\%$	80 A
Duty cycle > 97%	Charging not allowed

For what regard the connection scheme, placing the voltmeter upstream of the ammeter results in a voltage drop across the ammeter, which equates to a power loss directed towards the load. Consequently, the electric car will perceive a reduced voltage from the charging station due to the voltage drop across the ammeter, resulting in lower power reception. However, this approach is correct to the aim of the paper, as the measurement will focus on the EVSE rather than the load.

Alternatively, choosing a downstream connection may result in a voltage drop across the ammeter, leading to an underestimation of the power delivered by the EVSE. Furthermore, considering the V2G potential for reversing the energy flow, the connection effectively turns into a voltmeter downstream of the source, as the EV becomes the source. Nevertheless, this configuration remains appropriate for accurately evaluating the power supplied to the EVSE.

Regarding calibration, in general, it would be appropriate to define standard test procedures that establish the magnitude of the load current and the duration of the test, as well as defining minimum levels of accuracy to be met. This paper focuses on field calibration, so the possibility of varying the test voltage will not be considered; the test voltage will be imposed by the main electrical grid. Consequently, any influence of power quality phenomena on the accuracy of the meter being calibrated cannot be taken into account.

IV. PROPOSED CALIBRATION METHOD

In general, it would be appropriate to allow arbitrary variations of the load, in order to test the meter under all possible operating conditions. In detail, the meter integrated into an EVSE should work correctly regardless of the current level. This means that if a fast-charging supercar is connected (that entails a high current level), the ammeter will work at full scale. Instead, if a microcar is connected, the ammeter will work in a small part of the input range. This condition entails a reduced signal-to-noise level and resolution issues. The energy measurements must be assessed at different current levels, to verify the correct operation for all the possible working conditions. This would entail the need to implement an adjustable active or passive load both in direct current (DC) and alternating current (AC), a typical solution adopted by expensive laboratory equipment available on the market. Additionally, such equipment emulates the EV communication protocol (CP line) to simulate a charging process, tricking the EVSE into recognizing it as such.

Fig. 2. Proposed system block diagram

A simpler and cheaper way to test an EVSE is undoubtedly to use an EV as a load, interposing a reference wattmeter through appropriate connections. A connection scheme of the wattmeter to the charging station has already been developed [7]. However, with this system it was not possible to change the load current, because it is imposed by the EV OBC. This work proposes to extend the solution [7], implementing an electronic interface between the charging station and the EV capable of freely modifying the negotiation of the charging current level.

As explained before, the EVSE communicates to the EV the available current level through appropriate electrical signals. Typically, if the battery state of charge (SoC) is low, the Battery Management System (BMS) logic tends to draw the maximum possible charging current, to minimize the time required to fully charge the battery. In addition, when the battery is at a low SoC, there is usually ample capacity to accept a high charging current, without risking overheating or other adverse effects. This means that the vehicle draws exactly the maximum available current, as communicated by EVSE via the CP signal. By taking advantage of this behaviour, the communication between EVSE and EV can be hacked with a MIM (Man In the Middle) technique: the available current value can be modified, in order to force an EV to draw a desired test current level. In Fig. 2 a block scheme of the approach is illustrated. The proposed calibrator is composed by a reference wattmeter, a connection box (already presented in [7]) and a MIM communication device, that will be illustrated in the following.

The topic of cybersecurity risks associated with EVSE is not explored in the article, while this research acknowledges using the MIM approach for testing purposes, at the same time it's crucial to recognize the potential for malicious actors to tamper with the charging process. A hacker could take control of the EVSE and interrupt or slow down the car's charging, the scientific community should prioritize developing robust safeguard measures to mitigate these cybersecurity threats.

A. Hardware implementation

The EVSE CP output line passes through an intermediate device, where the duty cycle is arbitrarily varied before sending the new signal as an input to the EV. The simplified electrical scheme of the realized circuit is shown in Fig. 3.

The realized MIM device must implement the circuitry of an OBC on the input side and emulate the behaviour of an EVSE on the output side [11]. It's important to note that communication between the two is bidirectional: the EV needs to be informed of the available current (see tab. 2), while the EVSE needs to detect when the vehicle is connected and ready for charging (see tab. 1). An Arduino Due board has been adopted as programmable unit. It has to:

1. acquire PWM_{IN} input signal from the EVSE estimate its duty cycle,
2. provide the PWM_{OUT} signal according to the calibration test requirements but always lower than the maximum possible detected;
3. read the peak voltage ($READY_{IN}$) to determine the EV status;
4. communicate the EV status to the EVSE coherently ($READY_{OUT}$).

In Fig. 3, the network D1, R2 and R3, together with M1, realizes the input scheme of standard [8] (see Fig. 1). Opportunely driving M1 it is possible to signal the vehicle state B or C (task 4 of previous list). The network R4, M2 and R5 implements a level shifter circuit to adapt the signal to the microcontroller input logic level (task 1). On the other side, the PWM_{OUT} signal must be amplified by a comparator to be compliant with the standard [8] and R8 implements the required $1k\Omega$ series resistor (task 2). In conclusion D1, C1, implements a peak detector, R9 and R10 implement a voltage divider in order to adapt the peak voltage to the analog input of Arduino Due board (task 3).

Fig. 3. Simplified electronic schematic of the realized circuit.

Fig. 4. State diagram of the implemented FSM.

B. Firmware implementation

The proposed MIM device has been opportunely programmed. First, it's important to note that the PWM_{IN} signal is connected to a timer counter input and another timer peripheral has been adopted for PWM_{OUT} . The tc_lib and the pwm_lib open-source library from [10] have been used as drivers for those peripherals. Hardware timers offer superior accuracy, precision, and reliability compared to software timers, making them preferred for the specific application. For the $READY_{IN}$ and $READY_{OUT}$ pin respectively a analog input and a digital output have been used.

A Finite State Machine (FSM) has been developed for modelling and controlling the behaviour of MIM device. State diagram of the implemented FSM is shown in Fig. 4. As can be seen, the first transition (from the *IDLE* to the *EVSE READY* state) occurs if a valid duty cycle is present at the input ($\delta_{min} < \delta_{in} < \delta_{max}$). Subsequently, if the peak voltage (V_{ev}) is less than a proper threshold (V_{th}), also EV is ready, and the system sets the $READY_{OUT}$ pin and moves to the *CHARGING* state. Of course, when the EV is full charged, V_{ev} become lower than V_{th} and the system goes back to *IDLE*.

In *EVSE READY* and in *CHARGING* the maximum available current (I_{max}) is always monitored. Loop transition happens also at the user input that allows to set the desired test current. The *set desired current* action corresponds to opportunely set the PWM_{OUT} duty cycle coherently to Tab. 2 but always lower than the detected I_{max} . *ERROR* condition can be detected, in particular $\delta_{in} < \delta_{min}$ indicates a disconnection at the EVSE side. *CRITICAL* error verifies if the V_{ev} become too low (this should never happen given the circuitry of Fig. 3).

Fig. 5. A picture taken during experimental validation tests.

V. MEASUREMENT SETUP AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The realized field calibration setup is based on the one presented in [7]. The connection box has been realized to interpose a reference wattmeter to power signals and to connect communication CP signals to the MIM device. The proposed calibration scheme is shown in Fig. 2. A Yokogawa WT500 has been selected as reference power and energy meter. An electric vehicle provided by the University of Campania and an EVSE located within the engineering department's internal square were employed for the validation testing. All equipment was conveniently mounted on a cart for field use (see picture of Fig. 5). The selected EV is a Renault Kangoo Z.E. (Zero Emission) van from 2020, while the EVSE under examination is a three-phase system equipped with two Type 2 sockets (3P+N+PE), capable of handling up to 32A and 400V AC, with a maximum power output of approximately 22 kW, compliant with the IEC/EN 62196-2 standard [9]. It is designed for recharging electric vehicles in "mode 3" in public environments, adhering to the IEC/EN 61851-1 standard [8]. Several tests have been carried out, each with a different current value. Given the desired energy measurement resolution of 1% and considering the EVSE meter's display resolution is only 100 Wh, the energy absorbed by the EV during each test should be at least 10 kWh. Table 3 reports the 4 most significant tests, starting from the minimum current of 6A up to the maximum of 32A. Note that higher test resolution entails longer test duration, in particular at low current. The results of the tests are provided in Tab. 4, where the EVSE energy measurement is compared to the energy assessment obtained from the reference wattmeter. The relative error results always less than the instrument resolution (1%).

TABLE III. TESTS

Test	Current	Energy	Duration
1	6 A	10.0 kWh	7:35 h
2	12 A	10.0 kWh	3:47 h
3	24 A	10.0 kWh	1:53 h
4	32 A	10.0 kWh	1:25 h

TABLE IV. RESULTS

Test	EVSE energy measurement	Reference energy meter	Relative Error
1	10.0 kWh	10.0244 kWh	0.25 %
2	10.0 kWh	10.0612 kWh	0.61 %
3	10.0 kWh	10.0552 kWh	0.55 %
4	10.0 kWh	10.0487 kWh	0.48 %

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The simplest solution for field calibration of EVSEs' metering subsystems is to adopt an EV as a load [7]. This entails a limitation in the arbitrariness of the test current. A solution to overcome this limitation has been presented. The proposed device can hack the protocol between EVSE and EV allowing the test current to be arbitrarily chosen.

Currently, efforts are underway to integrate MIM device with reference energy meter, to replace the Arduino Due board with a low-cost, battery-powered, and more powerful microcontroller-based system, capable of implementing the energy measurement function as well. This final device will facilitate periodic verification of the metering subsystem of EVSEs in compliance with the EU MID directive.

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